

Drift in local sensor data

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Highlights

- Data from automated sensors measuring parking lot occupancy are examined.
- Data come from eight different touristic parking areas in Germany.
- Manual counts were performed to validate automatic sensor data.
- Data show unsystematic and erratic drifts in the counts, leading to inaccurate occupancy data.
- Without further correction, data from sensors cannot be used for tourism recommender systems.

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Introduction

Parking areas are of particular interest to visitor management because they can serve as functional PoIs and therefore as a proxy for experience PoIs in the vicinity (Reif, Schmücker, et al., 2023).

In order to provide accurate information to users, a recommender or dashboard needs accurate information from sensors.

We collected sensor data measuring vehicles driving to and from parking areas. The data come from magnetic underground coils and from edge cameras.

We had expected to find a balanced occupancy over the course of weeks and months, but we found a huge drift in different directions.

A lack of reliability in parking sensor data was reported in the literature: “Traditional counting sensors at the entrance and exit of garages have numerous errors that can accumulate from day to day. There is a lack of reliable methods to routinely recalibrate the counting sensors with ground truth.” (Tamrazian et al., 2015, p. 77).

Inaccuracies in the data and the pitfalls in the calculation of parking space occupancy are also known from other projects, on whose data we build here (Reif, Engelhardt, et al., 2023, p. 105 ff.). In this paper we show the possible forms and extent of such inaccuracy.

Expected data

Our fictitious data are thought to come from bi-directional pass-through sensors, and we want to assess the occupancy of a parking area accessible through one entry/exit.

We can calculate the number of cars in the area (occupancy, n) in time t_1 as the number of cars in t_0 plus the difference between incoming cars and outgoing cars in the period between t_1 and t_0 . This calculation is valid for any moment in time. In our examples, we look at data measured every hour. The data matrix has a timestamp, an in and an out value, and, derived from these, an hourly balance (in – out), volume (in + out) and occupancy, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Example data matrix for parking areas based upon bi-directional pass-through sensors

Timestamp	In	Out	Balance	Volume	Occupancy n
...	10
2023-05-01 08:00	5	0	+ 5	5	15
2023-05-01 09:00	15	5	+ 10	20	25
2023-05-01 10:00	65	15	+ 50	80	75
...

For tourism mobility (and thus also for a parking area which is mostly used by tourists), we expect a daily, weekly and seasonal component in a time series model for most destinations (Bi et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2022). We expect that the number of cars in the area (occupancy n) will increase in the morning and decrease in the evening (daily component), that it will be higher on weekends compared to weekdays (weekly component) and that it will be higher in high seasons compared to low seasons (seasonal component). High and low seasons are obviously dependent from the destination or PoI: While a beach destination will

have its high season in the summer, a skiing destination might experience its high season in the winter. Also, daily and weekly numbers might differ between PoI—think of a PoI that is closed on weekends or a PoI that is most active in the evenings, like a restaurant, bar or a club.

A prototypical time series model for a tourism-related parking area would predict the number of cars in the parking area at moment t based on the addition of a daily component D , a weekly component W and a seasonal component S plus some random error ε .

$$n_t = D_t + W_t + S_t + \varepsilon$$

However, and opposed to other types of time series, we usually do *not* expect to see a trend component in the data. A trend component is a long-term drift, the goes beyond daily, weekly or seasonal variations (Hamilton, 1994, p. 167 ff.).

We further assume that the number of cars in the area (n) cannot be bigger than the maximum capacity of the parking area and cannot be smaller than zero.

A fictitious plot of the expected number of cars in the area is shown in Figure 1: The curves show a daily maximum and a daily minimum (during the night) and higher peaks on the weekends. The curves do not exceed the maximum capacity of 1,000 slots and do not fall below zero, but have some cars standing overnight. As to the number of overnight cars, we expect that (a) this number will be small compared to the capacity of the parking area and that (b) it will not systematically increase or decrease over time, except for a seasonal component for campers or caravans standing in the area over night. The fictitious data indicate such a seasonal effect at the end of May (although it would probably be less abrupt in reality).

Figure 1: Cars in parking area, fictitious data

Drift in automatic counts

The following exhibits come from sensors in several German destinations. Most of the data cover the period from late 2022 until late 2023; the exact timing can be read from the x axis. On the y axis, the graphs show the number of cars in the parking area by hour (the occupancy). The background colour shows the total volume, ranging from dark blue (low traffic) to bright red (high traffic).

We analysed data from 14 camera-based sensors and 19 magnetic coil sensors. The eight graphs in the following section exemplify the problems we saw in the data. All 33 sensors, however, showed some drift or inexplicable deviations from the expected patterns.

Examples from camera-based sensors

We selected four examples from camera-based sensors showing different drift patterns.

Figure 2 (“Boedefeld”) shows very low volumes and a dramatic rise and fall in a short time span. In this case, we assume that a failure in the camera sensor (no data) and an unexplained massive drift overlap.

Figure 3 (“Westfalenhang”) shows a more realistic pattern, but it also exhibits negative values.

Figure 4 (“Ritzhagen/Am Hoppert, Willingen”) shows a constant negative drift until the beginning of February into a negative occupancy value (– 2500 and below).

In contrast, Figure 5 (“Ettelsberg Seilbahn”) shows a constant positive drift. However, the maximum value in the data, + 13,000, exceeds by far the capacity of the parking area, which is limited to 450 cars.

We usually see a leap in the data when the volume is high (red or yellow background).

Examples from magnetic coil sensors

Data from the magnetic coil sensors stem from LAB-TOUR SH, a research project similar to AIR (Reif, Engelhardt, et al., 2023). Here, we selected examples from motorhome stopover (Figure 6) and camping areas (Figure 7 and 8) The last example comes from a public parking area.

Figure 6 (“Malente”) shows a constant negative drift with relatively high volumes; the minimum value is below – 20,000. Figure 7 (“Spitzenort”), by contrast, shows a constant positive drift in the data.

Figure 8 (“Eutin”) shows a specific pattern of a more or less constant drift in times of moderate volume and sharper falls in time of high volume. Figure 9 (“Grömitz”) shows first a negative, then an positive trend only to fall and rise again on an even more pronounced level. .

Figure 2: Use case "Boedefeld"

Figure 3: Use case "Westfalenhang"

Figure 4: Use case "Ritzhagen/m Hoppert, Willingen"

Figure 5: Use case "Ettelsberg Seilbahn"

Figure 6: Use case "Malente"

Figure 7: Use case "Spitzenort"

Figure 8: Use case "Eutin"

Figure 9: Use case "Grömitz"

Automatic vs. manual counts

To shed more light on the unexpected results, we did manual counts on two different sites and on two different days in March 2023 on 24 quarter hours in the time from 9:00 to 12:00 and from 13:00 to 16:00.

Site 1 is located in the small town of Arnis (Schleswig-Holstein, 54°38' N, 9°56' E). It is a parking area with a broad driveway equipped with *two* magnetic sensors, each counting on two channels (in and out). The entry lane is not structurally separated from the exit lane. Site 2 is located in the town of Kappeln (Schleswig-Holstein, 54°40' N, 9°56' E). Here we have a parking area with *one* driveway for exit and entry. One magnetic sensor is counting ins and outs on two separate channels.

There are 24 counts per sensor (24 quarter hours). There are four sensors (two locations with two directions each). So in total there are $24 \times 4 = 96$ readings for automatic sensors and 96 manual counts. The 48 readings for Arnis include both channels from the two sensors.

The difference between sensor and manual count is zero in 37 out of 96 cases (39%), < 0 in 24 out of 96 cases (25%) (the automatic count yielded more vehicles than the manual count) and > 0 in 35 out of 96 cases (36%) (the automatic count yielded fewer vehicles than the manual count).

For the exits (OUT) there is a balance of 0 (the manual count did not show more or less vehicles than the sensor counted), of which + 3 in Arnis and - 3 in Kappeln. For the entries (IN) there is a balance of + 45 (the manual count showed 45 vehicles less than the sensor counted), of which - 46 in Arnis and + 1 in Kappeln.

The sensors count 146 % (146 automatic vs. 100 manual counts) in Arnis IN, 104 % (84 vs. 81) in Arnis OUT, 98 % (51 vs. 52) in Kappeln IN and 94 % (44 vs. 47) in Kappeln OUT.

As a result, the occupancy in the case of Kappeln differs only slightly between automatic and manual counts (Figure 10). However, even after one day with only moderate traffic, there is a difference of two vehicles: occupancy is + 7 for automatic counts while it should be only + 5. During the day, the maximum difference between automatic and manual sensors was + 6 (automatic sensors gave 21, manual counts only 15 cars). Having six cars more when there should be 15 is an overestimate of 40%.

In the case of Arnis we see an underestimate of occupancy during the first half of the day and then a gross overestimate during the second half. At noon, the difference is - 20 (automatic count was 35, manual count 15), while at the end of the day the difference was + 43 (automatic count was 62, while manual count was 19). Having 43 cars more when there should be 19 is an overestimate of 226 %!

Figure 10: Occupancy over 24 quarter hours

Conclusion

Real data from two different sources show many unsystematic and erratic drifts. Without correction or manipulation, these raw data can neither be used to convey occupancy rates in online recommender systems nor as valid input data for models.

Remains the challenge to correct the obviously erroneous data. We discussed different solutions, among them a reset during the night or a reduction of “surpluses” over several days. However, a valid solution is still to be obtained.

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Notes

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